

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada suniy intellektning ingliz tilini o'rganishdagi o'rni, uning afzallik tomonlari til o'rganish jarayonidagi ahamiyati, uning imkoniyatlari va haqiqiy hayotdagi ishlatilishi ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: interaktiv o'rganish, Personalizatsiya, Tilni va madaniyatni o'rganish, sun'iy intellekt asosidagi til o'rganish dasturlari

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается роль ИИ в изучении английского языка, его преимущества и значение в процессе изучения языка, его возможности и применение в реальной жизни.

Ключевые слова: интерактивное обучение, персонализация, изучение языка и культуры, языковые программы на основе искусственного интеллекта.

Abstract. This article examines the role of artificial intelligence in learning English, the importance of its advantages in the process of language learning, its capabilities, and its use in real life.

Keywords: interactive learning, personalization, language and culture learning, artificial intelligence-based language learning programs.

In recent years, significant attention has been paid to education in our country, especially in teaching foreign languages and creating broad opportunities for young people to learn foreign languages. In this context, numerous decisions by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, regarding education and the study of foreign languages can be cited as examples. One of these is the "Decision on Measures for the Development of Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan" (2017): This decision emphasizes the need to enhance the quality of English language teaching and to provide the younger generation with modern knowledge by increasing the role of the English language in educational institutions.

Additionally, a state program adopted in 2018 aims to develop Uzbekistan as a competitive state in the global education arena by 2030. It focuses on promoting English language teaching and the assimilation of educational programs in English. The overall goal of these decisions and initiatives is to equip Uzbekistan with specialists who possess the necessary knowledge to participate in global development processes. Furthermore, proficiency in English creates expanded opportunities and fosters international cooperation.

The significance of artificial intelligence (AI) in accelerating these processes is substantial. Currently, the development of AI technologies has fundamentally transformed the language learning process. This transformation is particularly important for millions of people who use global languages, such as English. With the help of artificial intelligence, language learning can not only be fast and efficient but also tailored to meet individual needs (Goh, 2021). This article will explore the importance of artificial intelligence in the language learning process, its capabilities, and its real-world application.

The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Language Learning.

The influence of artificial intelligence (AI) on language learning manifests in several aspects. These include:

Personalization: AI allows for tailored learning experiences that meet the specific needs of learners. While traditional classes often aim to deliver the same content to many students, AI-based programs can analyze each user's unique strengths and weaknesses, offering personalized learning plans (Dziubich, 2020). This customization increases student engagement and makes learning more effective.

Interactive Learning: Artificial intelligence can provide students with an interactive environment for language learning. For instance, through various applications, learners engage in dialogues and simulations to practice the language. This interactivity plays a crucial role in developing students' speaking skills (Goh, 2021). Additionally, interactive learning enhances the quality of lessons and contributes to better outcomes.

Learning Language and Culture: AI also assists in learning not just the language, but the associated culture as well. For example, programs offer students opportunities to explore English-language customs, proverbs, and idioms. This process aids in understanding the cultural context of the English language (Dziubich, 2020). The speed and convenience of AI, which can simultaneously address multiple tasks, play a significant role in helping students achieve proficiency in the language.

Extensive Resources and Materials: The abundance of resources and materials available through artificial intelligence greatly aids students in learning English. Programs provide a variety of video, audio, and interactive materials designed for language acquisition (Goh, 2021). These resources expand students' opportunities for independent learning beyond the classroom. It can be confidently stated that AI serves to make students' independent explorations much more effective and beneficial.

Some notable AI-based language learning programs include:

1. Duolingo: Duolingo makes the language learning process engaging and interactive through the use of artificial intelligence. The program assesses users' proficiency levels and offers personalized learning paths (Duolingo, n.d.).

2. Babbel: Babbel also employs AI to provide tailored lessons for learners. Additionally, the program features a variety of interactive exercises for studying grammar and vocabulary (Babbel, n.d.).

3 Rosetta Stone: This program enhances the language learning experience for students. With AI-powered speech recognition technology, learners reinforce their understanding of new words during the learning process (Rosetta Stone, n.d.). It also ensures that their leisure time is used effectively.

Like any technology, artificial intelligence (AI) has its limitations. For instance, AI-based programs often struggle in human-centric situations, such as emotional connections or physical interactions. Human teachers still play a crucial role in motivating students and providing support. Additionally, the ability of AI to offer users sufficient understanding may also be limited (Dziubich, 2020). While AI can provide students with vast amounts of information and knowledge, the human element remains paramount.

The importance of artificial intelligence in language learning, especially in English, is continually increasing. Personalized, interactive, and diverse resources provided to learners enhance the effectiveness of the educational process. However, the expertise of human teachers can never be fully replaced. Thus, the integration of AI with traditional teaching methods opens up new opportunities for language learning and offers the potential for more effective educational processes in the future (Goh, 2021). Furthermore, the proper use of AI can be beneficial for many young people in their independent language studies.

However, artificial intelligence can never fully replace the experience of human teachers. Human teachers build personal connections with students, understand their emotions, offer encouragement, and provide support throughout the learning process. They also have the ability to integrate various teaching styles, ensuring that students are approached based on their individual needs.

Therefore, the integration of artificial intelligence and traditional teaching methods opens up new opportunities in language learning. Teachers can utilize artificial intelligence tools to enrich their lessons, personalize learning experiences, and deliver more effective instruction. In the future, this harmonious combination of approaches will contribute to making language learning more efficient and engaging. Furthermore, we are witnessing the significant impact of artificial intelligence on the independent language learning of many young people.

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